

Equitable Compensatory System and Efficiency of the Cameroon Customs Administration

Dr. Aloumedjo Zam Thierry*

Email address: aloumedjo@gmail.com

Abstract—This paper explores the concept of compensation and benefits in HRM, its link with organizational performance and perspectives for a better and more equitable compensatory system in the Cameroon Customs administration. In that vein the author based its study on theories relating to equity and fairness and an in-depth analysis of the economics of Social Credit's philosophy. It must be recalled that much has been written about these concepts, but so far there is no integrated conceptual framework available for the Cameroon customs administration. Our goal here is to develop such a framework and ameliorate the existing pattern. We do this in a number of steps, starting with a presentation of the existing approaches, models, theories with respect to compensation system, equity and performance. The research methodology used is based on a mixed approach that implies a triangulation of qualitative and quantitative methods in order to address efficiently the research problem. I conclude with the presentation of recommendations and suggestions for further research. The sample for the study is comprised of 70 employees drawn from the 3895 personnel constituting the Cameroon Customs administration. A total of 70 questionnaires were distributed to selected employees. Out of these, 50 questionnaires were duly filled and returned. From analysis it appears that 75 % of the participants indicated that strategic planning of HR can effectively lead to efficiency of the Cameroon Customs administration. It is therefore recommended for organizations to put in place compensation and benefits schemes based on clearly defined and objective performance criteria. Furthermore the mechanism for distribution should be transparent. The author advises use of electronic means.

Keywords— Compensation; benefits; Cameroon Customs; organizational performance; The Economics of Social Credit; equity.

I. INTRODUCTION

According to literature review, compensation and benefits are tools conceived to motivate employees and attain organizational performance. It was first of all conceived by the classical theories or capitalism with pioneer like Adam Smith who believed that compensation permitted to improve the performance of workers and later on developed by modern theories with authors like Stacey Adam or Maslow that implied the effect of employee's information and skills in determining earnings in the labor market and who above a simple tool to instill performance, saw in it motivators and means for social, psychological, political and economic regulators. Determining and developing compensation and rewards program in organizations in today's labor market and ensure sustainability in the future is a great challenge faced by many organizations nowadays in the sense that a well-structured program with a good balance of wages, benefits and rewards will support an organization to remain competitive.

In that line, this paper tries to outline an equitable process for compensating employees in the Cameroon Customs administration. Although much has been said and done about compensation and benefits schemes in the customs department for it to be equitable for yielding individual and corporate performance, so far an integrated system bridging such concepts with organizational performance seems not to have been sufficiently explored. Moreover in the present functioning of the Customs administration, it appears clearly that customs revenues objectives and social climate are not satisfying as figured out by official statistics and speeches of the hierarchy. One of the main issues observed about it on employees for the past years is repeated several complains concerning the "inequitable" character of motivational schemes put in place by the state and ministry managers.

In order to find an answer to the research problem which is about the importance of the equitable process for compensating employees with regard to the efficiency of the Cameroon Customs administration. In other words what are the intrinsic implications of compensation and benefits schemes? How can they be applied efficiently? Do they have an impact on the efficiency of the organization? Is the present scheme in the Cameroon Customs administration satisfying? It is believed that an equitable compensation and benefits system will enhance efficiency of the Cameroon Customs department. To demonstrate such a hypothesis, a mixed approach including both a quantitative and qualitative data analysis will be adopted in order to better understand and answer research questions (Martens 2001).

The benefits of this research can be identified at the theoretical, methodological and managerial levels. Theoretically the concepts explored led us to the fact that mastery and proper implementations of such policies are useful for any organization that looks for performance and effective organizational culture. The limitations of the concepts and theories studied were also brought out in the sense that they did not take into consideration the case of specific contexts and organizations such as African administration and their specific realities. Methodologically the paper tried a mixed methodological analysis in order to better understand and answer the research problem. It further extended the scope of scientific methods explored in a study as it involved interviews; Performance tests; observations; follow up focus groups and document analysis. In managerial terms it puts at the disposal of managers in general and the customs administration of Cameroon in particular, tools to better up their organizational performance and job satisfaction

in a context marked by the inefficiency of the human resource management policy put in place.

This paper comprises three main parts which are first the conceptual and theoretical frameworks; secondly the methodological approach and thirdly conclusions and contributions of the research.

II. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORKS

Here we shall analyze the literature review (i), present other key related concepts (ii) and theories (iii).

II.1. Literature Review

A literature review is defined as a search and evaluation of the available literature in a given subject or chosen topic area. It documents the state of the art with respect to the subject or topic you are writing about. It surveys, synthesizes, critically analyses the literature in a chosen area. Our literature review will focus on the concepts of compensation, benefits and efficiency. For it to be relevant, an emphasis was put on western classical and non classical major scholars as from the 1990's considering the abundance of literature during that period and the modern perspectives attached to developments in that area of study. This part of our work consists in demonstrating briefly the familiarity with the body of knowledge concerning the chosen topic and establishing the credibility of our work.

i) Compensation

Severally defined, compensation is referred to as payment to an employee in return for their contribution (labor) to the organization (Gerhart and Milkovich, 1990). The most common forms of compensation include direct financial compensation (wages, salaries, bonuses and commissions provided at regular and consistent intervals); indirect financial compensation (leaves, retirement plans, education, and employee services) and non-financial compensation (career development and advancement opportunities, opportunities for recognition, as well as work environment and conditions). It is also defined as a systematic approach to providing monetary value to employees in exchange for work performed (Chandra Mohan Patnaik, 2012). Compensation is determined by a number of factors (Fair Wage committee's report) such are: the degree of skill, the strain of work, the experience involved, the training involved, the responsibility undertaken, the mental and physical requirements, the disagreeableness of the task, the hazard attendant to the work and the fatigue involved.

Compensation systems are important for the organization but are more often neglected by the DRHM (Gupta and Shaw, 2014). Literature on compensation is extremely rich (Paidan Hong, 2017). Compensation is output and the benefit that employee receive in the form of pay, wages and also same rewards like monetary exchange for the employee's to increases the Performance (Holt,1993). It has an impact on the employee's perception of the organization (Howard Adler & Richard Ghiselli, 2015). Compensation has effect on employee's job satisfaction and permit to avoid turn over and contestations (Muguoungo, 2015). The strategic nature of

compensation in management is not sufficiently explored (J. Trevor and Ian Larkin, 2012).

Determination of Compensation is usually provided as base pay and/or variable pay. Base pay is based on the role in the organization and the market for the expertise required conducting that role. Variable pay is based on the performance of the person in that role. Organizations usually associate compensation/pay ranges with job descriptions in the organization.

It has been noticed that while employees tend to focus on direct financial compensation when contemplating their rewards, according to the McKinsey Journal, for individuals who are relatively satisfied with their salary, it is the non-financial rewards that tend to be more effective in contributing to long-term employee engagement.

ii) Benefits

Employee benefits refer to various types of non-wage compensation provided to employees in addition to their normal wages or salaries. It is also known as benefits in kind. Examples of such benefits include: housing; group insurance ; disability income protection; retirement benefits; daycare; tuition reimbursement; sick leave; vacation ; social security; profit sharing; employer student loan contributions; conveyancing; domestic help (servants) ; and other specialized benefits. They aim at increasing the economic security of staff members, and in doing so; improve worker retention; motivation and job satisfaction across the organization. Employer-sponsored benefits are a primary concern of executives and employees alike (Shaun Pichler and Brian Murray, 2009).

Benefits play a critical role in social and economic infrastructures as well. Benefits programs supplied by employers often end up filling gaps in national health and retirement systems. (Ľuba Tomčíková, 2009). Both financial and non-financial rewards have a role in influencing job satisfaction, which ultimately impacts employee performance. (Mussie T. Tessema, 2013). Employees with different education levels and positions perceive different employee benefit impacts; and employee benefit programmes have greater influence on younger employees' job performance (Jon-Chao Hong, 2013).

Employees' benefits play a great role in the fight against stress-related problems in organizations (Sue Wheeler and Dawn Lyon, 1992). They are an important incentive for the employee's motivation (Gunkel, 2006). The efficiency and effectiveness of the employee's benefits system will see into it that employees get the best working environment. This in turn will enable to meet the set objectives of employing more employees and retaining them to increase productivity, market share and outwit the competitors (Podmoroff, D, 2005).

iii) Efficiency

The concept of efficiency, first used in the 1590s, derives from latin "efficientia" meaning "power to accomplish something," literally referring to efficient power; efficiency; influence. Across literature, it has been defined in various ways. The concept of efficiency expresses a specific form of rationality, used in attempts to control a changing situation by bringing it into conformity with a vision of how the world

works (JK Alexande, 2009). In a more general sense, it is the ability to do things well, successfully without waste. It refers to the capacity to produce a specific outcome with a minimum amount of unnecessary effort. Efficiency implies three concepts which are: technical, productive, and allocative. Thus technical efficiency addresses the issue of using given resources to maximum advantage; productive efficiency of choosing different combinations of resources to achieve the maximum benefit for a given cost; and allocative efficiency of achieving the right mixture programmes to maximize benefits (S Palmer - 1999). Efficiency (doing things right) differs from effectiveness (getting things done) in the sense that while the former relates to the ratio of useful output to total input, the latter refers to the ability to achieve a desired result. For example, two companies may achieve the same result but the first one used longer working hours and energy to achieve the desired results while the second used minimum time and efforts to attain the same objectives. In that case the first company is said to be effective while the second will be efficient. This implies that efficiency involves effectiveness in its conception. The following formula illustrated to that effect:

$EFFICIENCY = EFFECTIVENESS \text{ (Achieving the desired goal)} + USEFULNESS \text{ (Ratio of useful output to total output)}$

II.2. Presentation of Other Key Related Concepts

In order to relate efficiently the concepts of compensation and benefits to performance, the author deemed it necessary to present the organization of the Cameroon customs administration as well as the economics of social credit and catholic social teachings in the vein of promoting the idea that economic and political systems should be the servants of the people and not the other way round as it is today in our system.

i) Cameroon customs administration

The customs administration is defined in its structuring and functioning by Decree N° 2013/066 of 28/02/2013 signed by the Head of State of Cameroon, organizing the Ministry of Finance in the Republic of Cameroon. The missions of the Customs administration are the followings:

- Tax mission: the Customs administration collects taxes and customs duties which are paid into the public treasury. Customs thus contributes to more than 30% in the realization of Cameroon's State budget;
- Economic mission: consists in the protection of the national economic space and the encouragement of the country's economic development. This involves the fight against fraud, smuggling, trade facilitation, management of customs economic regimes, the fight against compensatory measures and dumping, the control of competition rules;
- Assistance mission: Due to its presence at the borders, Customs is required to carry out missions on behalf of other administrations. It thus provides its assistance to various State services, notably: the Ministry of Defense in controlling the entry of weapons, munitions and harmful substances, and the Ministry of Public Health through the control of Drugs and the quality of food;
- Surveillance Mission: the surveillance of land, air, and maritime entry and exit points on the customs territory is

provided by the DGC. This surveillance helps to fight against illegal trafficking (drugs, money laundering) and organized crime.

The organization of the Customs administration is structured as follows:

- A Department of Resources and Logistics;
- A Division of International Cooperation and Tax Bases;
- A Division of Legislation and Litigation;
- A Division of Customs Investigations and Surveillance;
- A Division of Recovery, Statistics and Information System;
- A Division for the Control of Financial Operations of External Trade and Exchange;
- An information and communication Unit;
- Division of Studies, Security and Trade facilitation;
- A Customs Training Centre;
- A Special Customs Intervention Squad.

The Personnel of the Customs is organized as follows:

Customs staff consists of civil servants and non civil servants. The civil servants include:

- The sedentary personnel, working in principal offices in charge of the determination of the basis of calculation and collection of customs duties and taxes. It is the civilian personnel;
- The active personnel, working in the surveillance units (subdivisions, Brigades, Posts). These personnel fulfills the mission of surveillance of land, sea and air frontiers, the conducting and putting of goods at customs disposal. They wear the uniform of the customs. We find these personnel at central services as well;
- The other civil servants (of the Treasury, Statistics, Water and Forestry, Documentation ...), who perform various functions within the Customs Administration;
- The non-civil servant staff is composed of contract officers of the administration and State agents, all governed by the Labor Code.

ii) The economics of social credit and catholic social teaching

In his preface to *The Economics of Social Credit and Catholic Teaching*. Dr. Heydorn points out that our present economic system is intrinsically dysfunctional, and consequently “economically, politically, culturally, and environmentally unsustainable”.

Catholicism and Social Credit are both opposed to the doctrines of materialism (dialectical materialism) and class struggle, the suppression of private property and enslavement and subordination of the individual. The idea is that economic and political systems should be the servants of the people and not the other way round as it is today in our economic system. Social credit could be explained in the following salient points (C.H. Douglas, 2014):

- The economy exists to provide people, as efficiently as possible, with the goods and services that they need to survive and flourish;
- The present established system is inherently unbalanced due to shortage of purchasing power;

- The capital costs that are generated exceed the consumer incomes that are simultaneously distributed. The gap is intensified by net savings;
- The vast majority of the money supply exists in the form of bank credit and most of the bank credit is issued in the form of a repayable debt;
- The conventional palliatives of the existing economic system lead to financial crisis, lack of job satisfaction and shortage of organizational performance;
- Credit to employees and other people should be issued free of debt, equitably and fairly in order to curb financial crisis, lack of job satisfaction and shortage of organizational performance. This is justified morally by the fact that each individual is rightly regarded as a shareholder in his economic association, administration or organization in general;
- The consequences of a Social Credit monetary reform would be the establishment of absolute economic security for every citizen in place of poverty and the threat of poverty, increasing leisure in place of servility.

The benefits of such a system it is that it provides solution for an equitable and fair redistribution of wealth in the organization that will favor organizational performance, justice and equity in the organization specifically and the society as large as it is based on the principle of the common good, or the Law of Love stated in the Holy Bible: "Love your neighbor as yourself" (Matthew 22.39). This could be a good remedy against frustration, stress, turnover and shortage of performance in some organizations such as the Cameroon Customs administration.

The Social Credit financial system follows from the discovery and explanations of truths of the purely natural order also comports and the proper role of the social order in the life of mankind and accordingly the true purpose of economic association is to deliver the goods and services which individuals desire, and to do this with the least amount of trouble to anyone (Oliver Heydorn, 2014). Social Credit is not tainted with Socialism nor Communism, and is worthy of close attention (Social credit and the catholic doctrine, 1939). Since Social Credit, in line with our preceding Articles, shows itself to be so respectful of the supremacy of spiritual values, of social peace, of private ownership, and individual liberty, there is therefore, no serious cause for ranking it amongst those forms of Socialism condemned by the Church (George - Henri Levesque, 1936).

The rules of the economic game and the institutions necessary for giving effect should be determined not by what is most beneficial to the powerful few, nor by what enhances the status or aims of any collective, but by the common good of individuals. That 'common good' consists in the fulfillment of the true purpose of economic association: the delivery of those goods and services that people can use with profit to themselves with the least amount of human labor and resource consumption as proposed by the principles of the Economics of Social credit (The distributists review, 1936). It appears odd with a humane perspective that money is not a good with intrinsic value, but a medium of exchange created out-of-thin-

air by bank's loans and therefore should be at the service of human king and not the reverse. Given the injustices inherent in capitalism, socialism, as well as the mixed economy, it is about time that an economic system that transcends the traditional spectrum be presented for serious study (Oliver Heydorn, 2007).

II.3. Related Theories on Employees' Compensation and Benefits

Our theoretical framework is made up of theories that explain our research problem and permit us to attain our objectives. In that vein our analyses will be based on Reinforcement and Expectancy theory; Equity theory and Agency theory; historical wage theories (subsistence theory, just price theory, surplus-value theory, wages fund theory); modern wage theories (marginal productivity theory and human capital theory)

It provides a brief description of the said theories, its limitations, a summary of the analysis of the theoretical framework and possible critiques. This will enable me to propose orientations for a better job satisfaction in Cameroon Customs administration and subsequently organizational performance.

II.3.1. Reinforcement and expectancy theory

Victor's Vroom Expectancy theory (or expectancy theory of motivation) is given a review in the Encyclopedia, this theory asserts that an individual will behave or act in a certain way because they are motivated to select a specific behavior over other behaviors due to what they expect the result of that selected behavior will be.

In other words, the motivation of the behavior selection is determined by the desirability of the outcome. However, at the core of the theory is the cognitive process of how an individual processes the different motivational elements. This is done before making the ultimate choice. The outcome is not the sole determining factor in making the decision of how to behave.

Expectancy theory is about the mental processes regarding choice, or choosing. It explains the processes that an individual undergoes to make choices. In the study of organizational behavior, expectancy theory is a motivation theory first proposed by Victor Vroom of the Yale School of Management.

Victor H. Vroom (1964), in his theory defines motivation as a process governing choices among alternative forms of voluntary activities, a process controlled by the individual. The individual makes choices based on estimates of how well the expected results of a given behavior are going to match up with or eventually lead to the desired results.

According to Vroom, motivation is a product of the individual's expectancy that a certain effort will lead to the intended performance, the instrumentality of this performance to achieving a certain result, and the desirability of this result for the individual, known as valence.

Expectancy theory is made up of three components: expectancy, instrumentality, and valence. Which are presented as follows:

- Expectancy: effort → performance (E→P)

- Instrumentality: performance \rightarrow outcome (P \rightarrow O)
- Valence: V(R) outcome \rightarrow reward

II.3.2. Equity theory

Considered one of the justice theories, equity theory was first developed in the 1960s by J. Stacy Adams, a workplace and behavioral psychologist, who asserted that employees seek to maintain equity between the inputs that they bring to a job and the outcomes that they receive from it against the perceived inputs and outcomes of others (Adams, 1963).

According to Decenzo and Robbins (2012) and Gupta (2011), Stacey Adam's Equity theory focuses on determining whether the distribution of resources is fair to both relational partners. Equity is measured by comparing the ratio of contributions (or costs) and benefits (or rewards) for each person.

The Equity theory is based on the fact that people value fair treatment which causes them to be motivated to keep the fairness maintained within the relationships of their co-workers and the organization.

The structure of equity in the workplace grounded on the ratio of inputs to outcomes. Inputs are the contributions made by the employee for the organization.

Equity theory therefore focuses on determining whether the distribution of resources is fair to both relational partners. It proposes that individuals who perceive themselves as either under-rewarded or over-rewarded will experience distress, and that this distress leads to efforts to restore equity within the relationship.

Stacey Adam in his works focuses on determining whether the distribution of resources is fair to both relational partners. Equity is measured by comparing the ratios of contributions and benefits of each person within the relationship.

Henceforth, as long as the ratio between these benefits and contributions is similar. Much like other prevalent theories of motivation, equity theory acknowledges that subtle and variable individual factors affect each person's assessment and perception of their relationship with their relational partners (Guerrero et al., 2005).

According to Adams (1965), anger is induced by underpayment inequity and guilt is induced with overpayment equity (Spector 2008). Payment whether hourly wage or salary, is the main concern and therefore the cause of equity or inequity in most cases.

Employees want to be treated with equity and want to feel that their contributions and work performance are being rewarded accordingly. If an employee feels underpaid then it will result in the employee feeling hostile towards the organization and perhaps their co-workers, which may result in the employee underperforming taking into consideration inputs and outcomes.

The implications of the Equity theory are that, the manager should be equitable in managing personnel of the customs administration in order to guarantee motivation; fairness and personnel retention. This taking into consideration the fact that, employees determine what their equitable return should be after comparing their inputs and outcomes with those of

their coworkers. This concept is referred to as "social comparison".

II.3.3. Agency theory

The agency theory is a supposition that explains the relationship between principals and agents in business. (Jensen and Meckling, 1976).

Agency theory is concerned with resolving problems that can exist in agency relationships due to unaligned goals or different aversion levels to risk. The most common agency relationship in finance occurs between shareholders (principal) and company executives (agents). It is a useful framework for designing governance and controls in organizations.

The first scholars to propose, explicitly, that a theory of agency be created, and to actually begin its creation, were Stephen Ross and Barry Mitnick, independently and roughly concurrently. Ross introduced the study of agency in terms of problems of compensation contracting; agency was seen, in essence, as an incentives problem. Mitnick introduced the now common insight that institutions form around agency, and evolve to deal with agency, in response to the essential imperfection of agency relationships (Barry M. Mitnick, 2006).

The conflict of interest and agency cost arises due to the separation of ownership from control, different risk preferences, information asymmetry and moral hazards. The literatures have cited many solutions like strong ownership control; managerial ownership; independent board members and different committees can be useful in controlling the agency conflict and its cost (Brahmadev Panda, N. M. Leepsa, 2017).

The implementation of a control mechanism depends on the amount and contents of the public and/ or private information that exist in the domain of the managerial accounting system. The disseminated information and the concurrent variables surrounding the agency relations are also vital elements in creating any control system (Mohammad Namazi, 2012).

Some authors have in turn suggested that large outside owners might have a role to play as monitors of the management and might thus enhance performance (Shlefer and Vishny, 1986) as well as Zeckhauser and Pound, 1990). On the other hand, the private benefits literature suggests that high ownership concentration may lead to the extraction of the firm's resources by the dominant owners at the expense of other shareholders (Barclay and Holderness and Bebchuk 1999). Both insider and outsider ownership concentration have a positive and statistically significant effect on firm performance.

II.3.4. Historical wage theories

Wage and salary, income derived from human labor. Technically, wages and salaries cover all compensation made to employees for either physical or mental work. Historical wage theories include the subsistence theory of wages; the wage-fund theory; the labor theory of value; the residual-claimant theory of wages; the bargaining theory of wages; the marginal productivity theory of wages. Supporters of these theories advance that the test of an economic theory should be its predictive power.

The subsistence theory of wages, advanced by David Ricardo and other classical economists, was based on the population theory of Thomas Malthus. It held that the market price of labor would always tend toward the minimum required for subsistence. If the supply of labor increased, wages would fall, eventually causing a decrease in the labor supply. If the wage rose above the subsistence level, population would increase until the larger labor force would again force wages down.

The wage-fund theory held that wages depended on the relative amounts of capital available for the payment of workers and the size of the labor force. Wages increase only with an increase in capital or a decrease in the number of workers. Although the size of the wage fund could change over time, at any given moment it was fixed. Thus, legislation to raise wages would be unsuccessful, since there was only a fixed fund to draw on.

The labor theory of value advocated by Karl Marx, believed that wages were held at the subsistence level by the existence of a large number of unemployed.

The residual claimant theory of wages, originated by the American economist Francis A. Walker, held that wages were the remainder of total industrial revenue after rent, interest, and profit (which were independently determined) were deducted.

According to the bargaining theory of wages, there is no single economic principle or force governing wages. Instead, wages and other working conditions are determined by workers, employers, and unions, who determine these conditions by negotiation.

The marginal productivity theory of wages, formulated in the late 19th century, holds that employers will hire workers of a particular type until the addition to total output made by the last, or marginal, worker to be hired equals the cost of hiring one more worker. The wage rate will equal the value of the marginal product of the last-hired worker.

It should be underlined that the marginal-productivity theory is a guide to long-run trends in wage determination and applies more generally than the bargaining theory of wages.

II.3.5. Modern wage theories

In the rank of modern wage theories we can identify the behavioral theories of wages and the human capital theory of wages.

Based on research studies and action programmes conducted, some behavioral scientists have also developed theories of wages. Their theories are based on elements like employee's acceptance to a wage level, the prevalent internal wage structure, employee's consideration on money or wages and salaries as motivators.

Human-capital theory which is a refinement of marginal-productivity theory holds that earnings in the labor market depend upon the employees' information and skills. The idea that workers embody information and skills that contribute to the production process goes back at least to Adam Smith.

II.3.6. Research variables

A variable is defined as anything that has a quantity or quality that varies. The dependent variable is the variable a

researcher is interested in. An independent variable is a variable believed to affect the dependent variable.

II.3.7. Research hypotheses

A research hypothesis (H) is the statement created by researchers when they speculate upon the outcome of a research or experiment. Based on our research question which is: How can the compensation and benefits system be reformed for an efficient Cameroon Customs administration? We can infer the following hypotheses:

H₀: Compensation & benefits system and Cameroon customs administration's efficiency are not inter-related

H₁: The more Compensation and benefits system is equitable, the more Cameroon customs administration will be efficient.

II.3. Summary of the Theoretical and Conceptual Frameworks

Exploring the concept of compensation and benefits in HRM, its link with our present economics system and perspectives for a better and more equitable compensatory system led us to a literature review analyzing the key concepts of Compensation, benefits, Cameroon Customs, organizational performance, The Economics of Social Credit and equity. This was later enriched by our theoretical framework with related theories on Reinforcement and Expectancy theory; Equity theory and Agency theory; historical wage theories (subsistence theory, just price theory, surplus-value theory, wages fund theory); modern wage theories (marginal productivity theory and human capital theory). It should as a result be understood that compensation and benefits are tools conceived to motivate employees and attain organizational performance. It was first of all conceived by the classical theories or capitalism with pioneer like Adam Smith who believed that compensation permitted to improve the performance of workers and later on developed by modern theories that implied the effect of employee's information and skills in determining earnings in the labor market and who above a simple tool to instill performance, saw in it motivators and means for social, psychological, political and economic regulators.

II.4. Critiques of the Theoretical and Conceptual Frameworks

The above-mentioned literature review that explored the various concepts of compensation, benefits, HRM, equity and organizational performance, has clearly established an integrated conceptual framework available for the combination of the said concepts. Therefore bringing out the contributions of the present research on the theoretical, conceptual and managerial domains. It appears thus that Employees' benefits and compensation play a great role in the fight against stress-related problems in organizations (Sue Wheeler and Dawn Lyon, 1992). They are an important incentive for the employee's motivation (Gunkel, 2006). The efficiency and effectiveness of the employee's benefits and

compensation system will see into it that employees get the best working environment. This in turn will enable to meet the set objectives of employing more employees and retaining them to increase productivity, market share and outwit the competitors (Podmoroff, D, 2005). But this cannot be achieved separately as there is the need to establish equity, transparent informational and contractual relationships in between the employer and employee as well clearly defining the performance expectations and related motivational scheme for the employee to identify his expectancy and instrumentality. However the overviewed literature did not permit us to present a model that fits developing countries. Furthermore no clearly defined features for equitable compensation and benefits schemes or contractual obligations are established in favor of a public administration as all the literature was exclusively referring to commercial and Industrial Corporations that aim profits not always general interest. Above that managerial aspect, limitations on the methodology used can be identified as they were limited to a qualitative approach not providing quantitative answers to the problem nor clear and concrete illustrations that is needed in an empirical study like our own.

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

We shall focus on the research design, the target population, the sampling frame, the sample and sampling techniques as well as the research instruments, data collection procedure, the data processing and analysis.

III.1. Choice of Methodology and Justification

In this study, the researcher adopted the concurrent triangulation design that implies converging both quantitative and qualitative data in order to better understand and answer research questions (Martens 2001). According to Cresswell (2012) and Wallen (2001), a mixed methods research design is a procedure for collecting both quantitative and qualitative approach in a single study to understand a research problem. The design makes use of both quantitative and qualitative data collection methodologies such as: Interviews; questionnaires; Performance tests; observations; follow up focus groups and Document analysis. The mixed research design approach presents a great advantage according to Cresswell (2012) in the sense that the combined use of both qualitative and quantitative methods provides a better understanding of the research problem. In fact, when one type of research either quantitative or qualitative is limited to address a research problem or research questions. The multiplicity of view points, biased and unbiased; subjectivity or objectivity; qualitative or quantitative will permit to obtain more detailed information.

III.2. Methodology Technical Characteristics

Here we shall deal with demographic information, samples and sampling, structures and themes of questionnaires, field work realities and statistical analyses and inferences.

III.3. Demographic Information

TABLE 1. Compensation and benefits schemes for a Cameroon customs officer.

N°	Types of remuneration	Amount paid in average for an inspector of customs	Criteria for determination of amount paid	Periodicity
1	“protocoles”	73,72 USD (41572 FCFA)	The amount is paid on the basis of the grade of the individual	Monthly
2	“ Remises”	202,57 USD (114 230 FCFA)	The amount is paid on the basis of the grade of the individual	Every three months
3	“ Special funding”	110 USD (61 979 FCFA)	The same amount is paid indifferently of the grade. No specific criteria for determination.	Monthly
4	“ TEL”	25,54 USD (14232 FCFA)	The amount is paid on the basis of the grade of the individual.	Monthly
5	“ CAC”	274,56 USD (154 825 FCFA)	The amount is paid on the basis of the grade of the individual.	Every three months
6	wage	413,19 USD (233 000 FCFA)	The amount is paid on the basis of the grade of the individual.	Monthly

Source: Adapted from customs data by author

III.4. Samples and Sampling

Sample is defined as a part of a large population (Orodho and KIM, 2009), which is thought to be representative of the larger population. This is the reason why the above-mentioned sampling frame was chosen.

The sample for the study is comprised of 70 employees draw from the 3895 personnel constituting the Cameroon Customs administration. A total of 70 questionnaires were distributed to selected employees. Out of these, 50 questionnaires were duly filled and returned. 20 questionnaires distributed were not returned. We assert the response rate to 71 % around.

III.5. Structures and Themes of the Questionnaires

Questionnaires with both open ended and closed questions were used to establish the relationship in between the remuneration practices; career advancement; work life balance practices; motivation and efficiency of the Cameroon Customs administration.

III.6. Field's Work realities

Field research or fieldwork is the collection of information outside a laboratory, library or workplace setting. The author could not work in quiet and orderly place since managers and personnel dealt with the same issues several times, for short periods of time in a strong complexity and lack of data (Aktouf¹ (2006, p. 198).

III.7. Statistical Analyses and Inferences

The study sought furthermore to establish the perceived relationship between compensation, benefits system and organizational performance. In the Analysis of variance setting, the observed variance in a Particular variable is partitioned into components attributable to different sources of variation. ANOVA provides a statistical test of whether or not the means of several groups are equal, and therefore generalizes the t-test to more than two groups.

Below are the findings presented in Table below simulated in the researcher’s context and based upon Shifts and Ladders.

Equitable compensation and benefits policy were found significant to organizational performance (efficiency of the Cameroon customs administration) ($r = .219, p = .000$)

TABLE 2. Correlations between labor mobility, Workforce planning and organizational performance

Independent variable	Pearson correlation	Organizational performance (efficiency of the Cameroon Customs administration)
Compensation and benefits system	Sig. (1-tailed) N	.219 .000 259

Source: The author

III.8. Critiques of Research Methodology

Although this research was carefully prepared, I am still aware of its limitations and shortcomings. First of all, the research was conducted in the developing world context where access to information is still very limited. Secondly, the population of the experimental group does not systematically represent the majority of workers. Thirdly, the research in this area is scarce in Africa in general and in Cameroon in particular, the country of the researcher. Finally since the assessment of the pretest and post test was conducted by the author himself, it is possible to find in this study a certain degree of subjectivity.

IV. RESEARCH FINDINGS

In this part we shall present in one hand the results of our statistical analyses based on our hypotheses, research variables, literature and theoretical review as well as methodology. On the other hand we shall carry out the discussion of our study.

IV.1. Analysis Results and Interpretations

In order to describe and explore the link in between efficiency of the CCA and strategic planning of HR. Data of the Cameroon Customs administration were collected and furthermore analyzed.

The tables below show the demographic information related to the personnel of the Customs administration. We can observe that for the year 2016, we registered 416 men for 118 women. In 2015, 387 men for 111 women. In 2014, 366 men for 98 women, the same figures in 2013. In 2012, 337 men for 87 women. In 2011 306 men for 75 women. And in 2010, 285 men for 59 women.

The researcher focused his studies on the most recent data i.e. 2017 as represented by the table 3 below:

TABLE 3. The civil branch of the Customs Administration.

Grades	Men	Women	Total
Senior customs inspectors	67	5	72
Inspectors	120	48	168
Senior customs controllers	36	10	46
Controllers	88	40	128
Assistant controllers	212	117	329
Agents	216	183	399
Total	739	403	1142

Source: The HRM Department of the Customs Administration

For the achievement of the objectives of this study, research hypotheses were formulated and tested based on the literature review on HRM practices and compensatory system as well as organizational performance. The statistical test results (regression and correlation analyses) of each null hypothesis at 94 % confidence level.

TABLE 4. Interviews

	Frequency	Percentages
Strongly Agree	40	20
Agree	80	40
Neutral	10	20
Disagree	20	10
Strongly Disagree	20	10
Total	170	100

Source: Author

The table shows that 75 % of the participants indicated that equitable compensation, benefits system can effectively lead to efficiency of the Cameroon Customs administration.

The outcomes of this research work have clearly revealed that the independent variables (equitable compensation, benefits system) have a direct and positive correlation and influence over the dependent variable (efficiency of the Cameroon Customs administration).

This has been done through the following process: Demographic information; Response rate; examination of Research Hypotheses; Collective role of the independent variables on the dependent variable and Analysis based on research objectives. Those analyses were based on a correlation and statistics inferences in between the independent variable and the dependent one.

IV.2. Discussion

The objective of our study was to interpret and describe the significance of equitable compensation and benefits system on the efficiency of the Cameroon Customs administration. Comparing with the above mentioned literature review and theoretical frameworks, it appears that the advantages of the above mentioned independent variables (equitable compensation and benefits scheme) are as follows: job satisfaction; helps establish strong work ethics and enhance productivity; Credibility and Professionalism as stated by (White, Lawrence T. (2012-02-23). This is in line with authors cited above and the theories presented and relating to job satisfaction in the sense that effective strategic equitable compensation of workforce will avoid subjectivity, frustration, the feeling of inequity or bias and therefore underperformance and as such guarantee organizational performance. Moreover equitable compensation and benefits

scheme is beneficial in recruitment, training, selection and mobility in a standard way across the whole organization. This implying that Strategic an equitable compensation and benefits scheme have a significant impact on organizational performance as regards to the hypothesis formulated and to the research question.

However the literature review and theories above stated show limits in the sense that there is not enough tools concerning the topic as far as sub-Saharan public administration is concerned, the research methodology provided in the literature review is mostly if not only qualitative not providing enough quantitative materials. The said literature does not illustrate how compensation and benefits should be implemented with regards to equity, the tools for controlling and assessing the equitable form of the compensation and benefits schemes put in place. Moreover the field work reveals itself extremely difficult as the customs administration's data base system as far as financial information is concerned is surrounded with a lot of "mysteries" and secrets. Moreover the system is not computerized therefore making analyses archaic.

V. CONCLUSIONS

This study aimed at determining the link in between equitable compensation, benefits schemes and organizational performance focusing on the efficiency of the Cameroon Customs administration. The main problematic was on the importance and the mechanisms for the implementation of an efficient, equitable system of compensation and benefits schemes. The methodology used for that purpose was the concurrent triangulation design that implies converging both quantitative and qualitative data in order to better understand and answer research questions (Martens 2001).

Statistics show that 75 % of the participants indicated that equitable compensation, benefits system can effectively lead to efficiency of the Cameroon Customs administration. The outcomes of this research work have clearly revealed that the independent variables (equitable compensation, benefits system) have a direct and positive correlation and influence over the dependent variable (efficiency of the Cameroon Customs administration). This has been done through the following process: Demographic information; Response rate; examination of Research Hypotheses; Collective role of the independent variables on the dependent variable and Analysis based on research objectives. Those analyses were based on a correlation and statistics inferences in between the independent variable and the dependent one. The benefits of this research were identified at the theoretical, methodological and managerial domains.

This study is alongside the article of the same author entitled: "A comparative study in between a professional football team and the Cameroon customs administration" which revealed that the Cameroon Customs Revenue will pass from \$827.9 million a year to \$ 4232, 7 million which represents almost half of the Cameroon State budget if only real HRM policies were implemented.

Although this research was carefully prepared, I am still aware of its limitations and shortcomings i.e. the literature

review and theories above stated do not provide enough tools concerning the topic as far as sub-Saharan public administration is concerned, the research methodology provided in the literature review is mostly if not only qualitative not providing enough quantitative materials. In addition the population of the experimental group does not systematically represent the majority of workers and finally since the assessment of the pretest and post test was conducted by the author himself, it is possible to find in this study a certain degree of subjectivity.

In terms of research perspectives it is believed that the present research was not sufficiently explored and as such there is need to extend it to other Cameroonian public administrations which for the majority face the same realities. It should be furthered in the context of the customs department by conceiving effectively a real compensation, benefits system based on equitable and purely objective criteria.

VI. RECOMMENDATIONS FOR THE CAMEROON CUSTOMS ADMINISTRATION

From the above mentioned, the following recommendations are formulated towards the Cameroon Customs managers:

- There is a need to establish objectives principles for the calculation of all compensation and benefits. The author believes that in addition to the grade, performance indicators (punctuality, attendance, the number of files treated, observations of the hierarchy on the beneficiary, level of education, individual and collective contribution to the performance of the organization, the degree of skill, the strain of work, the experience involved, the training involved, the responsibility undertaken, the mental and physical requirements, the disagreeableness of the task, the hazard attendant to the work and the fatigue involved) should also be taken into consideration;
- The compulsory assessment of workers in view of compensating workers should be done by a special unit of the Directorate in charge of human resource of the organization and validated by the General manager of Customs ;
- The results of the said assessment should be done through a computerized system, known clearly by all the actors and published for visibility and transparency reason in the internal communication means of the customs department and should be subject to claims before the director in charge of human resource;
- The various compensations and benefits should be transferred in the workers' bank accounts in the same way with monthly wages. The said compensation and benefits should not be paid in cash except by authorization of the minister of finance. All the various compensation and benefits should previously be transferred to the account of the worker in a bank of first order before any other microfinance or other financial institutions to guarantee traceability and avoid possible fraud and manipulations of any sort;
- All compensation and benefits schemes must be centralized and distributed by the directorate in charge of

HR in order to achieve several other purposes such as assisting in recruitment, job performance, and job satisfaction. Such a system should be well – defined and uniform and should apply to all levels of the organization as a general system. The intermediaries of human resource director could be the chief of service of “affaires generals” in each sector or region;

- The global amount shared for any compensation or benefit should be transparent as well as mechanisms for distributing considering that with effective compensation management the workers and especially the managers will also enjoy clearer visibility into individual employee performance when it comes time to make critical compensation planning decisions as well as other strategic decisions on the career of employees following a career planning put in place ;
- A study on the global amount of compensation and benefits should be carried out among the various units to guarantee equity for the various grades and positions;
- The author suggest that seminars and trainings on the topic should be organized in order to make understand that compensation and benefits are not just “ money shared” but an instrument of motivation and performance.
- Even though the benefits called “fonctionnement” is not a statutory one, but considering the fact that it is money given every month to workers, criteria should as well be defined as far as the part allocated for workers and logistics are concerned by the directorate in charge of human resource to guarantee efficiency of the organization. Moreover the allocation of such money should be defended by each director in the board of directors presided by the GM like when budgets are defended at the parliament. The use should be controlled

by the unit in charge of audit and control who has to make a report to that effect.

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